

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE PANCREAS OF PESTICIDE-INFECTED RATS IN HYPERGLYCEMIA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to study the morphological changes that occur in rats with experimental diabetes mellitus after chronic exposure to pesticides for different periods of time over a period of 6 months. After decapitation, the pancreas of rats that received pesticides for diabetes mellitus during the first 3 months was studied. The 3-month response of the pancreas to pesticide exposure in diabetes mellitus was mainly manifested in the form of acute damage, with a relatively thickened pancreatic capsule, an uneven surface, and signs of vascular congestion.

Relevance of the problem. Currently, diabetes mellitus is the third most common disease in the world and is a global medical and social problem in the healthcare system of patients of all ages and in all countries of the world.

According to WHO, by 2030, 18-20% of the world's population will suffer from this disease, 80-90% of whom will have type 2 diabetes. The prevalence of diabetes in industrialized countries is 5-6%, and the incidence and progression of the disease are particularly high among people over 40 years of age. WHO predicts that by 2025, the number of patients with diabetes in developed countries will increase by 41%. Patients with diabetes mellitus are at risk of a decrease in quality of life, disability and death, and complications of all internal organ systems. Despite extensive experience in the treatment of diabetes mellitus, the majority of patients remain disabled. Therefore, they represent a serious medical and social problem.

Materials and methods: In the study, an experimental diabetes model was created in 182 white laboratory rats (at a mass ratio of 0.11 mg/100). White laboratory rats were divided into 3 groups. **Group 1** - intact rats - control group. **Group 2** - experimental group - a group of rats in which an experimental diabetes model was created in 50 white laboratory rats. **Group 3** - a group of rats chronically poisoned with pesticides under conditions of experimental diabetes.

Discussion and results:

The next period of the experiment was continued for 6 months. It was found that the response of the pancreas to the effects of pesticides in diabetes mellitus during the 6-month period was mainly manifested in the form of chronic damage, accompanied by a decrease in

pancreatic tissue, the growth of adipose tissue in the perimeter and stroma, and a decrease in its morphofunctional aspects. In rats with diabetes mellitus, chronic poisoning with pesticides for 6 months mainly revealed changes such as an increase in coarse fibrous connective tissue around the common pancreatic ducts, a decrease in the size of the acini, thickening of the secretions, the appearance of uneven blood vessels, a decrease in the size of the islets of Langerhans, an increase in the spaces in the stroma, and an increase in connective tissue between the lobes. This confirms that pesticides stimulate a sharp disruption of metabolism in the pancreas of diabetic rats, leading to the death of acinar gland epithelium and a sharp decrease in morphofunctional indicators.

Thus, it was found that in diabetes mellitus, under the influence of pesticides for a period of 6 months, the pancreas tissue decreased in terms of volume, morphologically, the cells were of different sizes, the acini were also divided into different sizes, the number of acini in the intercellular junctions increased, the number of endocrine cells in the islets of Langerhans decreased, the tissue was unevenly nourished in small-caliber and capillary blood vessels, focal hemorrhages, and the formation of intermediate edema, with the appearance of scarred foci. This confirms the ongoing atrophic and sclerotic processes in the pancreas.

Conclusions

In rats with diabetes mellitus, chronic pesticide poisoning for 6 months revealed changes such as an increase in coarse fibrous connective tissue around the common pancreatic ducts, a decrease in the size of the acini, thickening of their secretions, uneven blood vessel filling, a decrease in the size of the islets of Langerhans, an increase in the number of spaces in the stroma, and an increase in connective tissue between the lobes. This confirms that pesticides stimulate a sharp disruption of metabolism in the pancreas of rats with diabetes mellitus, leading to the death of the acinar gland epithelium, and a sharp decrease in its morphofunctional parameters.

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